

LASER-VISION INSPECTION SYSTEM FOR AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT (AFP) PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The advent of automated composite manufacturing processes has brought forward new opportunities to manufacture composite parts using more reliable, more economic and faster processes. In particular, Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) process attracts aerospace industry's interest due to its flexibility to manufacture complex shape parts. AFP is a technique that can be used to manufacture both thermoset and thermoplastic composites in which fiber tows impregnated with resin are pushed against the surface of the mold. While the head of the fiber placement machine is laying the fiber tows, heat and pressure are applied simultaneously [1]. However, since AFP is a fairly new process, inspection techniques are not fully developed to assure the quality of the part during layup process. Possible defects needs to be inspected range from deviation in fiber orientation and location, gap and overlap nonconformity, foreign object, fuzz ball, etc. In this paper, a new inspection technique has been introduced for inspecting geometrical engineering requirements for each layer of the composite during the layup time. This inspection technique is composed of a laser system synchronized with a vision system to identify any deviation of fiber angle, tow location and gap size from engineering tolerances. The philosophy of inspection along with required hardware is presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

Automation of composite manufacturing processes has improved productivity, repeatability and reliability. It has reduced wastage of materials and recurring cost by reducing labor time for hand lay-up. Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) technology is one of the popular automation manufacturing techniques that can be used in manufacturing of both thermoset and thermoplastic composites in which the composite slit tapes (which are called tows and contain fibers and resin) are laid on the tool surface. While the head of the fiber placement machine is laying the composite tows, heat and pressure are applied simultaneously [1]. A picture illustrating the fiber placement head is shown in Figure 1. AFP process enables direct layup into complex geometries, making subsequent forming unnecessary and therefore saving manufacturing time and cost.

Figure 1: Automated Fiber Placement head (courtesy of National Research Council Canada[2])

However, although manufacturing process is automated, inspection is still lagging behind and is mostly performed visually and manually. The irony of the automation of manufacturing is that some parts manufactured by “automated” techniques actually take longer to inspect than to manufacture. Figure 2 shows cycle time breakdown for Boeing 787 Fuselage Barrel sections 47 and 48 manufactured using AFP [3]. It clearly shows that “Inspect and Rework” consumes 63% of the total cycle time, which is the largest element in the Pie chart and it takes more than 2.5 times the “Program”, which represents the time spent for lay up using AFP [3].

Figure 2: Cycle time breakdown for Boeing 787 Fuselage Barrel sections 47 and 48

There are several types of defects occurring during AFP manufacturing process and required to be detected with inspection. The placement of the composite tows, at the boundaries of the part and also where the tows are dropped individually inside the part boundaries, can lead to ply location defects (Figure 3). Each tow should be placed at specific location within the tolerance specified by engineering drawing. Wrong placement of a tow can potentially cause severe damage to the performance of the composite part. Another type of defects that can occur during layup is tow’s angle deviation defect. This is a situation where the angle of the AFP-placed tows deviates more than allowable tolerance. Figure 4 explains this type of defect; red line indicates the actual angle of the tow while green dash line shows the nominal angle of the tow.

Gaps and overlaps are also common defects that may occur during AFP manufacturing process. The large gaps cause resin rich areas which in turn could initiate failure and too much overlaps can also create bumpy surface (thickness build-up). Both gaps and overlaps may cause out-of-plane waviness in adjacent plies which can lead to stress concentration as well. Several studies [4-6] have shown that gaps and overlaps reduce the strength and stiffness of a composite laminate. Figure 5 shows a typical gap between two composite bands.

Figure 3: Ply location defect

Figure 4: Tow's angle deviation defect

Figure 5: Gap size defect

Visual defects are other types of defects that may occur during AFP process. It includes, but not limited to, foreign object debris (FOD), twisted tow, tow waviness, bridging, fuzz ball (Figure 6).

In summary, a reliable inspection technique is essential to detect the aforementioned defects and to report any parameters which are out of the accepted tolerances. Unfortunately, there is currently no turnkey inspection system available for AFP process and most of the inspection is being performed manually and visually by technicians. This is very time-consuming, costly and not reliable in a sense that it is dependent to the level of the technician's expertise. This paper presents Laser-Vision inspection technique which brings new opportunities for AFP inspection.

Figure 6: Visual defects; (a) twisted tow, (b) tow waviness, (c) bridging

2. LASER-VISION PROCESS OVERVIEW

Laser-Vision inspection system, as its name suggests, consists of two subsystems; a laser projection system and a vision system. Both systems have been known to the industry for many years and their technologies are mature enough in their application. The laser projection system has been used in hand layup manufacturing of composites to show the manufacturing personnel the boundaries of a ply. It has also been used for kitting and nesting processes. Vision system has been used in many industries for visual inspection, FOD detection and measurement purposes. The Laser-Vision inspection system takes advantage of these technologies and introduces new application for AFP inspection by combining these two systems.

Laser-Vision inspection process starts by laser projector scanning targets all around the part being inspected. This way 3D location of the part is obtained for the laser projector. In order to project precisely at the right location, laser projector needs to scan at least six targets that are not located in a line prior to the projection. After scanning the targets, a set of geometrical shapes called "Inspection Features" are projected on to the inspection area. Each inspection requirement has its own "Inspection Feature" which will be presented in section 3. After projection, a vision system is positioned at a

proper location to capture an image of the layer and the “Inspection Feature” projected on it (Figure 7). The image is then transferred to inspection agent’s screen for decision making step where she/he determines the conformity or nonconformity of the section under inspection. Inspection results can be then archived for verification purposes. The laser projector system and the vision system should be working in synchronized manner to ensure fast and reliable inspection. Inspection of three different defects, namely ply location, tow’s angle deviation and gap size are addressed in the next section.

Figure 7: Laser-Vision inspection process

3. INSPECTION TECHNIQUE

Engineering tolerances are defined in engineering drawings as geometric dimensioning and tolerancing (GD&T) system. Deriving from engineering tolerances, inspection requirements for different types of defects are obtained. Laser-Vision inspection technique includes designing a geometrical shape called “Inspection Feature” corresponding to each inspection need. These “Inspection Features” contain information that enables one to perform inspection and make decision on quality of the part. The “Inspection Features” are then projected using a laser projector on the layer that is under inspection and inspection process follows as explained in section 2. As an example, three types of defects and associated “Inspection Features” are explained below:

- 1- Ply location defect:** Engineering tolerances require that the location of each composite tow to be within specific range. This requirement can be translated to a 3D curved box (in a general case) that if all tows are placed within this box, inspection requirement is met and if any of tows is placed outside of this box, there would be nonconformity. Therefore, “Inspection Feature” for ply location defect is a 3D curve box shown in Figure 8. Projected “Inspection Feature” for ply location defect on a composite part is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8: “Inspection Feature” for ply location defect

Figure 9: Projected “Inspection Feature” for ply location defect

- 2- **Tow’s angle deviation:** Engineering tolerances require that the angle of a composite tow placed by AFP to be within specific degree range ($\pm X^\circ$). This requirement can be translated to a reference point and a gage length defined by a double cross shape as shown in Figure 10. If the tow’s edge crosses the gage length, it indicates that the angle of the tow is acceptable and otherwise is indication of nonconformity. Projected “Inspection Features” for both cases are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 10: “Inspection Feature” for two’s angle deviation defect

Figure 11: Projected “Inspection Feature” for two’s angle deviation defect

- 3- **Gap size defect:** Allowable gap size defined by engineering tolerance (e.g. $\pm 0.XX$ ”) can be translated to an “Inspection Feature” as shown in Figure 12. If the gap size is less than the gage length defined by the double cross shape, it is acceptable and otherwise it is considered nonconformity (Figure 13).

Figure 12: Inspection Feature” for gap size defect

Figure 13: Projected “Inspection Feature” for gap size defect

4. TECHNICAL CHALLENGES

There are two specific challenges in inspection of AFP-made ply using Laser-Vision inspection system; first, the reflective properties of composite tows (wet shiny black look on black background) make it difficult to capture an image in which “Inspection Features” are visible (visibility challenge). Second, highly contoured parts make it difficult to project precisely.

To achieve precise projection on highly contoured parts, the angle of attack of the laser ray on the surface of the part under inspection should not exceed 30 degree. This is indicated as “Projection Rule” and is shown in Figure 14.

In order to overcome the visibility challenge, “Visibility Rule” should be followed. This rule indicates that if the camera is positioned inside a cone whose axis follows the law of reflection, it would be able to capture a clear image in which laser patterns are visible. This rule is demonstrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Projection and visibility rules demonstration

5. CONCLUSION

A new inspection technique, Laser-Vision inspection system, is introduced for inspection of Automated Fiber Placement manufacturing process. This inspection technique composes of a laser projection system and a vision system working in a synchronized manner to detect potential defects. The philosophy of inspection along with the inspection process is presented. Laser-Vision inspection system offers many advantages including but not limited to: faster inspection time, ergonomic inspection process, automation possibility, traceability of results and cost effective solution.

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